

ELIXIR Report of the 23rd RDA Plenary

ELIXIR RDA Focus Group

RDA Plenary 23 Report

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Introduction

This document has been prepared by [ELIXIR's RDA Activities Focus Group](#) to showcase the synergies and activities of the [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#) which may be useful for ELIXIR members operating in the life sciences domain. The RDA was launched as a community-driven initiative in 2013 with the goal of building the social and technical infrastructure to enable open sharing and re-use of data. The ELIXIR RDA Activities Focus Group has prepared twenty reports of [RDA Plenary events](#) to date containing overviews of highlighted RDA recommendations and outputs. This report contains highlights from various sessions of the RDA 23rd Plenary as a hybrid event in San José, Costa Rica, 12-14 November, 2024. Additional links to collaborative note documents and/or abstracts provided by the session chairs are included.

About the 23rd RDA Plenary

The 23rd RDA Plenary was a fully hybrid event with virtual and onsite participants interacting and accessing recordings of all sessions using the [Whova](#) conferencing platform. The event was hosted by the Consejo Nacional de Rectores (CONARE) in collaboration with Universidad de Costa Rica (UCR), Tecnológico de Costa Rica (TEC), Universidad Nacional (UNA), Universidad Estatal a Distancia (UNED), and Universidad Técnica Nacional (UTN).

The organisers reported impressive engagement in this year's event:

- 364 participants (194 onsite and 170 online)
- Attendance from 48 countries
- 5 Plenary meetings
- 51 Breakout sessions

Following this year's successful event the upcoming [24th RDA Plenary](#) will take place virtually 7–11 April, 2025.

RDA Group Acronyms

- Working Group - WG
- Interest Group - IG
- Birds of Feather - BoF
- Community of Practice - CoP

Notes section

Overview

This section contains more detailed notes by ELIXIR members at the event who reported back key info.

Note: not all sessions of the event had ELIXIR reporter coverage given the volume of sessions.

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Breakout 6: Evaluating Multi-Omics Data Standard Integration Challenges and Building Solutions

Breakout 7: (RDA-Ofc Mapping) Report and Plans

Breakout 7: Updates and community feedback for HarmonisedMatChem WG

Programme Overview

- On Monday (11 Nov) and Friday (15 Nov), co-located events and closed meetings are scheduled.
- This programme is based on the official [RDA's 23rd Plenary Programme](#) (last updated: 6 Oct)
- All date/time values are listed in UTC.

Monday, 11 November 2024

- [Co-located event: Interoperability Frameworks in the Global Perspective: FAIR-IMPACT](#)

Tuesday, 12 November 2024

Start	End	Session (with link to report if available)
13:00	14:00	Registration, check-in
14:00	15:30	Sustainable Science specifically Responsible Data in the Scientific Era
15:30	16:00	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
16:00	17:30	Findings on TRUST Principles Adoption
16:00	17:30	The global evolution of AI governance and the relevance of the AIDV-WG's deliverables
16:00	17:30	Towards FAIR Digital Twins: FAIR and Interoperability for Earth System Digital Twinning
16:00	17:30	FAIR4ML IG Activity Updates and Feedback
16:00	17:30	Proposal for IG: Data, process and NTRO in the creative and performing arts
16:00	17:30	Terminologies for Data Management & Quality of Data Management : Ensuring FAIR Principles
16:00	17:30	Evaluation of Research: Leveraging liaisons
16:00	17:30	Health Data Commons GORC profile: Methodology, Means, and Moving forward
17:30	18:30	Lunch Break
18:30	20:00	Adoption and Impact of RDA Outputs and Recommendations – Fireside Chats
20:00	20:30	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
20:30	22:00	Advancing Data Skills: Expanding the CODATA-RDA SoRDS Curriculum
20:30	22:00	The Repercussions for an Institution of a Research Data Commons
20:30	22:00	On the Path to Enhancing Crisis Management Through Advanced Digital Technologies
20:30	22:00	Building trustworthy data repositories through certification
20:30	22:00	Global open research commons: Recommendations, implementations, and profiles
20:30	22:00	Networks of Data Ambassador & Steward – Sharing experiences
20:30	22:00	Applying AI in Data Discovery
20:30	22:00	Converging PaN FAIR data activities around the world
22:00	22:30	Break
22:30	0:30	Onsite Poster Session, Minute-Madness
0:30	1:00	Drinks Reception

Wednesday, 13 November 2024

Start	End	Session (with link to report if available)
14:00	15:30	What do we actually mean when we talk about data versioning?
14:00	15:30	Implementing and Facilitating Data Review in Data Repositories
14:00	15:30	Agricultural Research Data Integrity
14:00	15:30	VREs/Virtual Labs/Science Gateways: Defining FAIRness badges for VREs
14:00	15:30	Challenging I-ADOPT
14:00	15:30	Gamifying RDM: The Data Hunters Card Game
14:00	15:30	Update from Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO4RS) WG
15:30	16:00	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
16:00	17:30	Sample Classification – Do we need an interdisciplinary classification vocabulary?
16:00	17:30	The Role of generalist repositories in the research data landscape
16:00	17:30	All About Terms and Ontologies (You Can Help!)
16:00	17:30	Effectively Utilizing Research Tools in Curation Processes
16:00	17:30	Who cares about the Uptake of Digital Research Infrastructures? Understanding use cases and needs
16:00	17:30	Practices, tools and the research data lifecycle
16:00	17:30	Creative engagement with research data
16:00	17:30	Reproducibility at RDA and beyond: What do we know and what do we need
17:30	18:30	Lunch Break
18:30	20:00	PIDs in the Gray Areas: Tackling the Challenges of Identifying Instruments, Facilities, and the Research Tools Continuum
18:30	20:00	Recommendations for handling Complex Citations
18:30	20:00	To whom does the “I” in FAIR belong? A cross-group discussion
18:30	20:00	Creating Personas – Introducing the Data Steward Career Tracks WG
18:30	20:00	A Dat(a) with Destiny: Cross-domain collaborations in the NFDI, and beyond
18:30	20:00	Assisting data infrastructures in making their data precisely identifiable and citeable
18:30	20:00	Technical Repository Service Providers: Community Engagement #2
18:30	20:00	Coordinating Dialogs in the FAIR Digital Object Landscape
20:00	20:30	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
20:30	22:00	Sustainable Data Infrastructures in Latin America
22:15	23:00	RDA for Newcomers Session (For those who are new to the RDA!)

Thursday, 14 November 2024

Start	End	Session (with link to report if available)
14:00	15:30	Data for the Environment – Connecting and Governing Data for Sustainability
15:30	16:00	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
16:00	17:30	National Data Services – Activities and Charter
16:00	17:30	FAIR Mappings – Let's start working

16:00	17:30	Active Data Management Plans: What are the actions that we need to realize them?
16:00	17:30	Introducing the Earth, Space, and Environmental Science Community of Practice
16:00	17:30	Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive or Confidential Data: FAIRness for Controlled Data and Processes
16:00	17:30	Evaluating Multi-Omics Data Standard Integration Challenges and Building Solutions
16:00	17:30	Training RDM? Teaching RDM? What is our future?
16:00	17:30	Gathering Metrics and Setting Boundaries: Reusing Collections as Data and the impacts of AI
17:30	18:30	Lunch Break
18:30	20:00	(RDA-Ofc Mapping) Report and Plans
18:30	20:00	Updates and community feedback for HarmonisedMatChem WG
18:30	20:00	Implementing CARE Principles: Indigenous Data Governance using the Local Contexts Hub
18:30	20:00	Abandon, Replace, or Expand: Cultivating Global Ecosystems for Legacy Data
18:30	20:00	Governing Open Agriculture and Agricultural Knowledge Commons
18:30	20:00	Ensuring Data Underlying Publications are Sustainable, FAIR, CARE, and TRUSTed
20:00	20:30	Networking Tea and Coffee Break
20:30	22:00	Closing the RDA 23rd Plenary Meeting

Reporting

Monday, 11 November 2024

Co-located event: Interoperability Frameworks in the Global Perspective: FAIR-IMPACT

 When & where: 13:00 – 16:00 CST | 19:00 – 22:00 UTC | 11 Nov

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes:

<https://www.fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/interoperability-frameworks-global-perspective-fair-impact-co-located>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- [FAIR-Impact](#): Formal links already exists with, via funded partners (EBI, UNIMAN/UK) and in kind contributors (UOXF/UK); ROcrate and FAIRsharing embedded in this project's activities
- [GORC](#) model: Several ELIXIR individuals have contributed (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström, Susanna Sansone); the model also helps Nodes and their activities to ensure all key elements are considered when a commons (of data, methods, tools, people etc) is built
- [WorldFAIR](#) interoperability framework: Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework ([CDIF](#)) - maybe something to look into, even if it may be too high level?
- Discussion on what interoperability is and means in different scenarios; the concept of 'vertical interoperability' in the context of the different stages of the research life cycle ([MaLDReTH](#)), eg from planning (eg DSW) to collecting (incl ELN) and publishing (generic and specific repositories)

Tuesday, 12 November

Plenary: Sustainable Science specifically Responsible Data in the Scientific Era

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 14:00-15:30, Aula Magna, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Mark highlight key results from [The State of Open Science 2023](#) report. Do we do anything to help researchers on copyrights/licensing data? It seems the top challenge from the report, along with understanding the requirements of data policies
- NIH has launched the [Data Sharing Index \(S-index\) Challenge](#) Promoting data sharing and developing a robust metric to reward exemplary data sharers. This Challenge aims to incentivize and reward data sharing excellence, promoting a new metric for assessing how effectively researchers share valuable data, driving a culture of openness in science.

Breakout 1: The global evolution of AI governance and the relevance of the AIDV-WG's deliverables

 Groups: [Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG \(AIDV-WG\)](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Edificio Educación Continúa

 Reported by: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes-The global evolution of AI governance and the relevance of the ...](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- The Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG (AIDV-WG) is wrapping up its activities focused on ethics, informed consent and secure processing environments for AI & data visitation (DV) and looking for input and adoption of its outputs:
 - [AI Bill of Rights Recommendation](#) (doi:10.15497/RDA00123),
 - [Guidance for Informed Consent](#) (doi:10.15497/RDA00121),
 - [Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and Data Visitation](#) (doi:10.15497/RDA00122)
 - [Guidance on Secured Processing Environments for AI and Data Visitation](#) (forthcoming)
- Brief overview of the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA) and AI innovation in the European Health Data Space (EHDS) regulation mapped to AIDV-WG outputs presented ([slides 29–53](#)) followed by examples of emerging governance approaches and challenges in many other regions (US, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Africa, Singapore, Philippines, Brazil, Chile)

... detailed report (bullet points or paragraphs)

Breakout 1: FAIR₄ML IG Activity Updates and Feedback

 Groups: [FAIR for Machine Learning \(FAIR₄ML\) IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium 2, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes-FAIR₄ML IG Activity Updates and Feedback .docx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- FAR₄ML aims to:
 - Define a life cycle for ML models and how to apply FAIR principles to each step.
 - Define a FAIR metadata model to describe ML models
- Task force 1: ML Lifecycle for FAIR₄ML
 - What are ML models? Data? Software?
 - Lifecycle for FAIR Machine Learning ([preprint](#))
 - Simplified process
 - Ongoing: How are FAIR principles relevant in each step
 - Planning FAIR₄ML White Paper in May 2025
 - Collaborates with Skills₄EOSC
- Task force 2: ML model metadata based on schema.org
 - Literature review, crosswalks, metadata schema
 - Reuses Croissant Dataset data model

Breakout 1: Terminologies for Data Management & Quality of Data Management : Ensuring FAIR Principles

 Groups: [Professionalising Data Stewardship IG](#), [Sensitive Data IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Allyson Lister, Marek Suchánek

 Agenda / Notes: https://www.rd-alliance.org/session_entry/joint-session-application-03-07-2024/ and

 Notes for paper P23 session - Terminology for data management

Slides: Session Terminology for Data Management P23 PresentationV2_12112024.pptx

Unfortunately, the start of this session had a number of technical issues, but got better after that.

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- They have defined a need for common terminologies for various concepts such as data, repository, instruments, and data-related roles. These terms are already partially addressed by existing Life science ontologies such as OBI and T4FS, so ELIXIR may have a role to play here but it is not strongly related.
- Once this WG is complete, we might wish to use the terminologies they create/recommend.

Romain David provided a brief introduction to the session (co-chair of Professionalising Data Stewardship IG, where Mijke Jetten is also a co-chair); then, a series of presentations followed:

- Anne-Sophie Bage: *Terminologies in Data Management Context* - mainly focused on presenting what is in their poster, identification of challenges, hidden properties and missing dissemination/documentation on certain terminology used in data management (e.g. data - typology of data, functional requirements on storages, etc.).
- Romain David: *Terminologies for Competence Centers* - explained what are competence centers in the context of EOSC and also the related OSCARS project: Community-based virtual hubs dedicated to fostering research excellence through training and knowledge transfer, and providing expertise, best practices and services in relation to Open Science.
- Paul Millar: *Terminologies for Data Services* - presented challenges and terminology used in PaNOSC.
- Alison Specht: *Terminologies for Data and Multilingual Challenges* - focused on diverse teams and related challenges, esp. terminology obstacles (synonyms, nuances, different meanings based on context, new concepts; recommendations: use a dictionary in a team, interactive DMPs, never assume that others know specific terminology, share problems, be careful with online translations (esp. with new concepts).
- Liise Lehtsalu: *Terminologies for Data Management Professionals* - issues are both with definitions of roles and services in data management: difficulty to map existing services and develop new ones, difficulty to compare services, challenge to the professionalisation of roles providing data management support; as a solution: extending RDM terminologies (e.g. CODATA RDM Terminology is limited) and professionalisation of roles providing data management support.
- Yvan Le Bras: *Terminologies for Virtual Research Environments (VRE)* - 3 areas of challenges: VRE scope (whole life-cycle, data-oriented), internal interoperability, external interoperability; using implementation choices of community to support their specific needs; FAIRness, transparency, openness e.g. via RO-Crate
- Pedro Correa: *Terminologies for Data in Machine Learning*

Breakout 1: Health Data Commons GORC profile: Methodology, Means, and Moving forward

 Groups: [Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 16:00-17:30, Aula Magna, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone, Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

 Agenda / Notes: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1pkrVTiphMTygeAXaoKAPshhivg_-9laM/edit

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- A new WG that the ELIXIR Health Data Focus Group to look at and maybe follow

- Work in progress to extend [DCAT-AP](#) with health specific health data properties: [HealthDCAT-AP](#)
- Their first step of this WG to Identify national-level health data commons through a systematic review
 - Ensure elixir members, building commons, are aware and involved if interested, and comment on the [questionnaire](#) this WG is building.
- ELIXIR-SE staff as co-chair, GA4GH member on speaker list

This new working group will create a health data commons profiling of the [GORC](#) International Commons Model that can then be used and expanded upon in the health data space to address FAIR and other relevant principles as well as to compare features. By generating machine actionable metadata that describes commons in a consistent, structured way, we will make visible the choices communities of practice make when implementing FAIR across health data commons.

Presentation also from Robert Grossman (Chicago) on USA Health Commons and Secure and Authorised FAIR environment (SAFE), trusted enclaves; Robert will be one of the chairs of this new WG.

Plenary: Adoption and Impact of RDA Outputs and Recommendations – Fireside Chats

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 18:30-20:00, Aula Magna, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

 [Outputs_Recommendations_Firesidechat_overall_slidedeck_20241112.pptx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- RDA Secretary General - Hilary Hanahoe
 - Distinguish work (outputs of the community) and business (impact, collaborations, visibility)
 - Many active groups, but also number of BoF sessions (new ideas)
 - Increasing visibility (in Latin America)
 - Challenging to find model for sustainability of such open organisations
- RDA groups (on their impact and outputs)
 - Sharing Rewards and Credit (SHARC) IG [in Spanish]
 - Professionalising Data Stewardship IG (PDS-IG), Liise
 - Two perspective (service and profession), two work tracks
 - Survey and landscaping reported
 - GORC IG, CJ Woodford
 - Typology and Definitions, GORC Model
 - Being adopted in ELIXIR but also other communities, organisations, incl. even NSF
 - Data Discovery Programs IG
 - Ten Principles to Improve Dataset Discoverability
 - Eleven quick tips for finding research data
 - Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG
- RDA TIGER and TIGRUS

Breakout 2: The Repercussions for an Institution of a Research Data Commons

 Groups: [Research Data Architectures in Research Institutions \(RDARI\) IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 20:30-22:00, Auditorium, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dTbaS4fNBIGUw7FXIb7Y5hbYE8ywn8qF/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- The group is working to applying the GORC model widely, including for institutional projects; since it can be used as a 'checklist' to ensure all relevant elements are considered
 - Can the elixir ecosystem of platforms and communities, along with its resources and services, be considered a Commons

Presentation also from Gerry Reilly on BioFAIR as Research Data Commons

Breakout 2: Applying AI in Data Discovery

 Groups: [Data Discovery Paradigms IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 20:30-22:00, Auditorium 2, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Applying AI in Data Discovery .docx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Interesting use cases on applying LLMs for data discovery
- Data Discovery Paradigms IG publication: [Ten principles to improve dataset discoverability](#)

Detailer report:

- Data Discovery Paradigms Interest Group (2016->)
 - Kicked off several RDA WGs since then
 - 2024 publication: [Ten principles to improve dataset discoverability](#)
- Use cases:
 - Use cases of applying LLM in enriching metadata (Mingfang Wu, Amir Aryani)
 - LLMs to classify towards "ANZSRC-FoR: The Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification - Fields of Research"
 - Finding: LLM output should be evaluated before deployed, and have a clear message that the output is from AI
 - Using LLM to Identify Topics (Amir Aryani):
 - Linking research topics, grants, and expertise
 - Leveraging Large Language Models for Data Discovery (Tianying Chen et. al.)
 - Experiences from study where users try dataset discovery using Microsoft Copilot

Special: Poster session (onsite)

 When & where (UTC): 12 Nov 22:30-0:30, Aula Magna, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [RDA P23 Poster Exhibition](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Posters presented by ELIXIR personnel:
 - [Unleash your Models! Flow your Data! "Parse, Don't Validate!" – turning the tables with Omnipy](#)
 - [Plan-Driven Data Management as a Service](#)
 - [FAIRsharing Educational: Supporting RDM best practices and enabling FAIR](#)
 - [Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions \(MARS\)](#)
 - [Metadata Harmonization at Scale: FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG](#)

Wednesday, 13 November

Breakout 3: Challenging I-ADOPT

 Groups: [Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology WG \(I-ADOPT WG\)](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 14:00-15:30, Classroom 40, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1nW2ghxUZc0bOCEcKmoZ8D0hSYnCCYuXP/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Perhaps something the Biodiversity and Plant Sciences Communities to look at, as well as generic practices for the EIP.

The Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property Terminology [I-ADOPT](#) Framework is an ontology primarily designed to facilitate interoperability between existing variable description models (eg ontologies, taxonomy, CVs). This effort has a strong focus on **variables observed in environmental research** because it leverages existing efforts to accurately encode what was measured, observed, derived, or computed in relation to the Earth systems. One of the challenges in representing semantic descriptions of variables (eg height, area fraction) is getting people to agree about what they mean when describing the components that define the variables. The I-ADOPT ontology addresses this by providing core components and their relations that can be applied to define machine-interpretable variable descriptions that re-use FAIR vocabulary terms. For example concentrations of DDT in site is described as mass of something (DDT) in something (site).

Now this WG is working on: (i) a validation via SHACL Shapes, and (ii) a compact representation via JSON-LD and validation via JSON schema.

Breakout 3: Gamifying RDM: The Data Hunters Card Game

 Groups: BoF

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 14:00-15:30, Auditorium, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Allyson Lister, Marek Suchánek

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Gamifying RDM: The Data Hunters Card Game .docx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- We may wish to participate or simply follow to see how gamification can be incorporated into ELIXIR workshops and conferences. This aligns nicely with the work currently approved by ELIXIR by Allyson and Xenia with the RDM social game in development, "Two Rooms and RDM".
- The card game is openly available and can be also customized according to specific needs of communities: Strubbia, C., & Soro, A. (2025). Data Hunters - role play card game (Version v1). Research Data Alliance (RDA), San Jose - Costa Rica. Alessandra Soro. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14713230>

Detailed notes

- AL: While I could not attend in person, as I was attending the PRO₄RS session as I thought it more immediately relevant to ELIXIR, I did pop in long enough to register my interest and state how ELIXIR is working on various RDM-based gamification ideas (at the moment, me and Xenia doing Two Rooms and RDM)

- AL:I added this to their notes: Apologies, but I cannot attend as I am in a parallel session, but I'd like to say that I'd love to be involved if any gamification IG is formed, at any level from member upwards depending on what roles you need filling. I do a lot of gaming, and am currently in the process of creating some RDM-themed card / social deduction games with support from ELIXIR (part of EOSC). Please let me know how I can help! 😊

Breakout 3: Update from Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software (PRO₄RS) WG

 Groups: [Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO₄RS\) WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 14:00-15:30, Auditorium 2, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software \(PRO...](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Outputs of the PRO₄RS WG could help with incorporating better wording around research software sharing in policies of ELIXIR members.

Detailed report

- 38 policies have been identified by the group as specifically dealing with software.
- I have commented that FAIRsharing currently has [209 policies](#) that either mandate or suggest software sharing, and that PRO₄RS is working with FAIRsharing via their WG co-chairs and our Community Champions (Hugh Shanahan, Timothee Aubourg) to ensure that we are sharing our information regarding these policies. It may also be that FAIRsharing can store appropriate metadata around research software policies; this can be determined through the lifetime of the WG. We would like our two projects to fully share data around sharing research software via our connection points with Hugh and Timothee.
- We worked through some examples of software policies and which attributes each policy had to show how assessment of policy metadata occurs.
- They asked if they should also include RDM policies that only mention software in passing; I suggested they ensure they regularly search FAIRsharing policies for new ones mentioning software, and ensure their info and FAIRsharing's info is shared across the two groups at regular intervals.

Breakout 4: The Role of generalist repositories in the research data landscape

 Groups: BoF

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vldqyrFolwIGKv2ksKGouY3SOgKPw1Po/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- For the Data Platform to monitor this work and continue ensuring the discipline-specific repositories are primary location for relevant data
 - Susanna seats on the [GREI Working Group of the Council of Councils](#) is to provide an assessment of the GREI's progress to date and to provide recommendations for the future of this initiative

The NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative ([GREI](#)), which brings together seven generalist repositories (Dataverse, Dryad, Figshare, Mendeley Data, Open Science Framework, Vivli, and Zenodo) to enhance support for NIH data sharing and discovery in generalist repositories. Improve the consistency and functionalities of these platforms, following the list of NIH desirable characteristics of data repositories; secondary mission is to raise awareness and help

researchers to adopt FAIR. Current activity is to define what the use cases are, so how they see the generalist repos are used by different stakeholders and how the latter would benefit from this harmonization.

Breakout 4: Effectively Utilizing Research Tools in Curation Processes

 Groups: [Research Tools and Data Curation Workflows IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 16:00-17:30, Classroom 40, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Effectively Utilizing Research Tools in Curation Processes.docx](#)

 [RDA P23 - Research Tools and Data Curation Workflows IG](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- FAIR Data and PIDs: Integrating Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) like DOIs and IGSNs into research tools can enhance FAIR compliance and metadata quality in life sciences.
- Interoperability Challenges: Research tool interoperability issues, including standardized schemas and flexible APIs, are critical for seamless data exchange across ELIXIR platforms.
- Data Stewardship Collaboration: Aligning institutional data stewardship roles and workflows with ELIXIR's framework can improve data curation, reuse, and infrastructure integration.

Session:

- Introduction to the Interest Group (IG)
 - Focus on Research Data Management (RDM) and Data Curation.
 - Established in October 2024 with co-chairs from Leiden University, KU Leuven, and RSpace.
- Case Studies Presented:
 - Integrating Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) in Research Tools (Xiaoli Chen, DataCite)
 - How PIDs support FAIR workflows.
 - Role of PIDs for researchers, institutions, and research outputs.
 - Overview of COPO (Felix Shaw, Earlham Institute)
 - Research Tool Interoperability for Easier Data Curation (Vaida Plankytė, RSpace)
 - Challenges in achieving vertical interoperability.
 - Case study on integrating material sample PIDs (IGSN IDs).
 - Need for standardized schemas, flexible APIs, and better communication between stakeholders.
 - Discussion on IG's Focus and Future Work:
 - Identifying friction points in selecting and maintaining research tools.
 - Improving collaboration between research institutions and tool providers.
 - Customizing research tools and workflows based on institutional needs.

Breakout 4: Reproducibility at RDA and beyond: What do we know and what do we need

 Groups: [Reproducibility IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 16:00-17:30, Classroom 2, Edificio Educación Continúa

 Reported by: Allyson Lister / Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Reproducibility at RDA and beyond: What do we know and wh...](#)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CetDWvNx4M9PakFfDnazoEa5aeTyhNpj/edit>

Slides: [RDA Reproducibility IG P23 Presentation.pptx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Coordination of activity related to reproducibility internal and external to RDA in order to develop a research agenda to improve reproducibility
- Forum to discuss reproducibility-related developments, tools, infrastructure

Detailed notes

- Reproducibility IG has been working to surface the different groups working in reproducibility and share that information with others.
 - Established 2014 - Hiatus 2019
 - Reestablished 2023
 - Objectives:
 - Forum for a discussion of RDA developments relating to reproducibility
 - Identify and discuss relevant tools, workflows, and computational infrastructure
 - Develop a research agenda aimed to increase reproducibility
 - What is reproducibility, how is it different from reusability and replicability?
 - "A result is reproducible when the same analysis steps performed on the same dataset consistently produce the same answer."
- P23 [Mapping activity](#) of reproducibility-related initiatives internal and external to RDA

Breakout 5: Recommendations for handling Complex Citations

 Groups: [Complex Citations WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 18:30-20:00, Auditorium, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [link](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Main problem to be solved is how to manage the citation of e.g. a large number of datasets, which journals often do not support (typically no more than 20-30)
- Connection to RO-Crate is already established - WG aims to pick up the thread for the adoption phase

... detailed report (bullet points or paragraphs)

- Main problem to be solved is how to manage the citation of e.g. a large number of datasets, which journals often do not support (typically no more than 20-30)
- Preliminary outputs of the "Complex Citations WG" were presented, and participants were able to vote and comment on them through a menti.
- Recommendations are available in this [slide set](#)
- A "Complex Citation Object" is a PID-identifiable object that contains a number of Linked Digital Objects (the metadata necessary to identify the digital objects that support the research, or scholarly product. This includes data, software, physical samples, images, and video - not papers.
- Technically oriented solution - conceptual for now, next step is adoption by e.g. DataCite, journals,
- Already working with RO-Crate - will pick up that thread for adoption phase

Breakout 5: To whom does the "I" in FAIR belong? A cross-group discussion

 Groups: [FAIR Data Maturity Model WG](#), [GORC International Model WG](#), [GORC IG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 18:30-20:00, Aula Magna, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1vXLfJgT1l3RqYgwLF26pyfv-1kTp57dj/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- As and if GORC gets used within ELIXIR then having a way to define its maturity would be useful.

Several years after the RDA maturity model was developed this remains a document; meanwhile two [EOSC FAIR Metrics focused Task Forces](#) and a funded project ([OSTrails](#)) work to create metrics, tests, and benchmarks to harmonize the over 28 [FAIR assessment/assistance tools](#). Now it seems that the RDA maturity model WG has moved to work with the RDA GORC WG to define the maturity of a Commons However, it is still unclear how this will be done and how this work will connect and reuse the activities under EOSC.

Breakout 5: A Dat(a) with Destiny: Cross-domain collaborations in the NFDI, and beyond

 Groups: BoF

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 18:30-20:00, Classroom 2, Edificio Educación Continúa

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

 BoF – A Dat(a) with Destiny: Cross-domain collaborations in the NFDI, and beyond

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- **Cross-Domain FAIR Data Collaboration:** Insights from NFDI and ARDC show how FAIR data management supports interdisciplinary research, aligning with goals for biological and health data integration.
- **Interoperability & Shared Infrastructure:** The development of common services (e.g., PIDs, metadata, knowledge graphs) across NFDI consortia mirrors work in biomedical data standards and repositories.
- **Community-Driven Research Data Management:** Examples like food security modeling and Indigenous data governance highlight the need to foster cross-sectoral partnerships in life sciences.

Presentation:

- Introduction to NFDI (Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure)
 - NFDI is a decentralized, bottom-up initiative supporting data sharing across 26 research consortia, spanning life sciences, humanities, natural sciences, and engineering.
 - Goal: Organize research data as a common good while fostering interoperability between different disciplines.
 - NFDI has dedicated sections addressing metadata, infrastructures, industry collaboration, legal aspects, and education.
- Cross-Domain Collaboration Case Studies
 - Food Security & Biodiversity (FAIRagro, NFDI4Earth, DataPLANT, NFDI4Biodiversity): Addresses climate change impacts on agriculture using integrated data from meteorology, soil science, and crop modeling. Uses climate scenario data (2036-2065, RCP8.5) for predictive modeling of wheat yield and protein content.
 - R:hovono - Historical & Object-related Vocabularies (NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Objects, FactGrid, BARTOC, Base4NFDI): Develops a shared classification system for historical, archaeological, and social sciences research. Uses linked open data and semantic web technologies for improved data integration.
 - Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC): Supports translational research on environmental challenges (e.g., bushfire impact analysis). Provides services for metadata, persistent identifiers, and indigenous data governance.

- Latin American Network for Open Science (LA Referencia): Focuses on open access and research data infrastructure for Latin America. Discusses mechanisms for FAIR data exchange and policy harmonization across regions.
- Common Challenges & Solutions in Cross-Domain Data Management
 - Trust & Collaboration: Overcoming discipline-specific barriers to enable shared research.
 - Interoperability: Creating common metadata standards and infrastructure to support data exchange.
 - Balancing Data Sensitivity & Openness: Ethical and legal challenges, especially in indigenous and cultural data.
- Future Outlook & Next Steps
 - Discussion on forming an Interest Group (IG) to continue collaboration.
 - Identifying best practices from NFDI, ARDC, and LA Referencia to enhance global research data infrastructures.
 - Strengthening links between NFDI and international frameworks like ELIXIR for biomedical and life sciences data integration.

Breakout 5: Technical Repository Service Providers: Community Engagement #2

 Groups: [Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers WG \(TRSPs WG\)](#)

 When & where (UTC): 13 Nov 18:30-20:00, Auditorium 2, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Allyson Lister

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ofWEB-rz3x9W536uRrcmFNriGAQd8k1H/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- This WG is concerned with the creation of a landscape analysis on repository attributes with a view to the ability for resources (including service providers) to self assess their own resources.
- They are keen to have community input, e.g. from ELIXIR

Full details are at [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Technical Repository Service Providers: Community Engagemen...](#), but the key point is that it will provide a lower barrier to repositories (including those within ELIXIR) to self report their attributes that would allow the community to have an indication of their trustworthiness; this is good for ELIXIR resource discoverability and visibility.

Thursday, 14 November

Breakout 6: FAIR Mappings – Let's start working

 Groups: BoF

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Edificio Educación Continúa

 Reported by: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1mDq5SjopwrSrs-9lpaCWqULPzEWWqceE/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Mapping data from one representation to another is often necessary when integrating data from different domains and creating these mappings often requires a significant amount of resources. While mappings are being shared and reused, there is a lack of common exchange formats and guidelines on how to enable their

discovery and widespread reuse. This is the third in a series of BoF sessions organised to establish the [FAIR Mappings WG](#).

- Collecting use cases ([template as GitHub issue](#)) and documentation on [the group's website](#) while developing: a classification scheme of mappings, technical recommendations, (meta)data models, and a framework for creating, sharing and reusing mappings

Additional notes:

- FAIR Mapping recommendation starting from FAIR-IMPACT recommendations: Use [Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings \(SSSOM\)](#) as far as possible (especially metadata), serialise as Linked Data, relying on widely used vocabularies that are shared according to the as FAIR principles, assign PIDs to individual mappings and collections of mappings
- FAIR-CORE4EOSC has developed a Mapping repository service and API [Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry \(MSCR\)](#)
- Next steps: Recruiting additional co-chairs, forming subgroups, schedule bi-weekly meetings

Breakout 6: Active Data Management Plans: What are the actions that we need to realize them?

 Groups: [Active Data Management Plans IG](#), [DMP Common Standards WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Marek Suchánek

 Agenda / Notes: [W RDA P23 Collaborative Notes - Active Data Management Plans: What are the actions that we ...](#)

 [2024.11-RDA-CostaRica-DMPs.pptx](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- DMP Common Standards for maDMPs is now starting more active maintenance mode due to activities in the OSTrails (Horizon Europe) project but also in DMPTool overseas.
- There is a movement towards creating a new working group on common maDMP API specification as DCS covers only the data model but not exchange and operations over maDMPs.

Presentations:

- Introduction to Active DMPs and Machine-Actionable DMPs (maDMPs)
 - Traditional DMPs are static, human-readable documents, while maDMPs use Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and structured metadata to enable automation.
 - The DMP Common Standards Working Group (WG) maintains the RDA recommendation for maDMPs and ensures interoperability.
 - There was also traditional Menti checking what people are in the room.
- Updates on DMP Tools and API Development
 - DMP Tool Improvements (Becky Grady, CDL)
 - Making DMPs fully machine-actionable, allowing API-based interactions and integrations.
 - New features: DOI-based DMP tracking, JSON-based metadata, ORCID, ROR, and funder registry IDs.
 - Plans to rebuild the DMP Tool with a new data model and structured templates.
 - Common API for DMP Platforms (Tomasz Miksa)
 - Developing an API for querying and updating live maDMPs.
 - Key goals: linking DMPs to repositories, funders, and institutions in real time.
 - Steps Toward FAIR, Interoperability & Automation.

- FAIR and Scientific Knowledge Graphs (Elli Papadopoulou, OpenAIRE)
 - Presented efforts in the OSTRails project relevant to maDMPs.
 - PTA Framework (Plan-Track-Assess) to integrate DMPs with FAIR evaluation tools and knowledge graphs.
 - Pilots across 15 national, 8 thematic, and 1 pan-European initiative to improve DMP interoperability.
- Maintaining the RDA DMP Common Standard (Marek Suchánek)
 - Updates planned for 2025 to refine metadata extensions, repository integration, and sustainability.
- Challenges & Future Work
 - Technical Complexity: Balancing user convenience vs. machine-readability in maDMPs.
 - Repository & Dataset Linking: Improving automated discovery of datasets/software related to DMPs.
 - Funders' Role: Encouraging adoption of structured templates instead of narrative-based DMPs.
 - Interoperability: Ensuring alignment between maDMPs and existing metadata frameworks.
- Next Steps & Future Goals
 - Submit a new Working Group proposal for the common maDMP API.
 - Enhance automation by improving machine-actionable question types, linking datasets, and integrating repositories.
 - Align with international standards to ensure cross-institutional adoption of maDMPs.

Breakout 6: Trusted Research Environments for Sensitive or Confidential Data: FAIRness for Controlled Data and Processes

 Groups: BoF

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 16:00-17:30, Auditorium, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Nn6EVsCWgVfAjXydOEHWaj6RKDTKeDzY/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Third BoF session supporting a working group proposal taking shape on [Trusted Research Environments \(TREs\) for Sensitive or Confidential Data: FAIRness for Controlled Data and Processes](#)
- Preparing to launch in early 2025, focusing on blueprints, interoperability, risk management, and FAIR for sensitive data.
- ELIXIR projects, regional TREs linked to ELIXIR Nodes, [UseGalaxy.eu](#) etc referenced in [draft case statement](#)

Breakout 6: Evaluating Multi-Omics Data Standard Integration Challenges and Building Solutions

 Groups: [Multi-Omics Metadata Standards Integration \(MOMSI\) WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 16:00-17:30, Classroom 2, Edificio Educación Continúa

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone and Allyson Lister

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Kp-ytPqtvY1KpBt-ezjMTYpalZDSEB7/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- The MOMSI WG's deliverables are tightly linked to the FAIRsharing collection (<https://fairsharing.org/5742>) they have created

- The outputs of this WG should be key documents for our various Omics communities.
- Bert has presented MARS (<https://github.com/elixir-europe/MARS>) that uses ISA-JSON and has matured at this year BioHackathon

... detailed report (bullet points or paragraphs)

- They have completed their first set of deliverables in time for this plenary as outlined in our case statement, which includes
 - Landscape Review of existing Omics community standards (Deliverable 1a), and
 - Multi-omics Standards Collection located at FAIRsharing (Deliverables 1b)
- The aim of this session is to collect any relevant feedback or proposed revisions community stakeholders may have on our first set of deliverables, including all supplementary training materials supporting WG Multi-omics standard record criteria selections aggregated under our FAIRsharing Multi-Omics Collection.
- Following VP23, they will start work on the next deliverable (crosswalk analysis of selected standard records aggregated under Deliverable 1b for identifying metadata reporting integration gaps and cross-domain standard element adoption opportunities).
- MOMSI WG Collection in FAIRsharing
 - You can highlight the relationships among these resources via FAIRsharing graphs
 - You can make the information accessible globally, even where e.g. google spreadsheets and others are not so easily accessed
 - You can see the live status of each resource, and see if any of them are e.g. deprecated
- MARS: Multi-omics Adapter for Repository Submissions
 - There are many repositories for various omics repositories at the EBI. Great for researchers, except that each have very different submission processes.
 - BioSamples is used at the EBI to link sample metadata with assay data among their various repositories.
 - MARS is a data brokering initiative for submission of multi-omics data
 - ISA-JSON used to exchange information
 - MARS is a common framework, which allows for decentralised data submissions
 - MARS will ensure consistent interpretation and validation of ISA-JSON containing metadata across repositories.
 - Stakeholders: ISA-JSON producing platforms (e.g. ISA-Wizard, ARC, SEEK, ISA-creator), data brokering platforms (e.g. Galaxy), and EBI repositories.
 - ENA and Metabolights are already on board with this system
 - In future, they wish to onboard EVA first and then the other repositories (conversations have begun with MGnify). They are also looking at using MARS-CLI as a Galaxy tool and producing a custom web interface.

Breakout 7: (RDA-OfR Mapping) Report and Plans

 Groups: [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 18:30-20:00, Auditorium, Plaza de La Autonomía

 Reported by: Susanna Sansone

 Agenda / Notes: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1hKC1VXRvRzv-zTIKcaTHDtWumFwYQFL4/edit>

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Perhaps the Tool Platform could review this categorisation, and consider its use
 - Prototypes: <https://adamvialsmoore-jisc.shinyapps.io/r-proto/>
 - <http://18.132.118.14/maldrethviz/>

- <http://18.132.118.14/maldreth-lf/>

This [Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG](#) addresses the categorisation of research tools, based on their features, functionalities and how they interoperate; thus do not plan to do a catalog of tools. They hope that better categorisation helps with discovery, use but also foster interoperable. The WG has developed (i) a harmonised research data lifecycle and crosswalk to existing models, (ii) a categorisation schema of digital research tools commonly used in each phase of the research lifecycle, MaLDReTH; and (iii) an online tool to facilitate and explore mapping the digital research data infrastructure landscape.

Breakout 7: Updates and community feedback for HarmonisedMatChem WG

 Groups: [Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG](#)

 When & where (UTC): 14 Nov 18:30-20:00, Classroom 40, Edificio de Ingeniería

 Reported by: Sveinung Gundersen

 Agenda / Notes: [link](#)

Key points relevant to ELIXIR:

- Relevance to "FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG" (FGA-WG) in that the two WGs are similar in scope, but for different domains.
- Approach very different:
 - "HarmonisedMatChem WG" defines recommendations starting on a very general level
 - FGA-WG oriented on pragmatism, building from the ground up.

Overview of WG work streams:

- Stream A: Collection, review and FAIR maturity assessment of the existing semantic artefacts
 - Review and application of existing recommendations, including:
 - Yann Le Franc, Luiz Bonino, Hanna Koivula, Jessica Parland-von Essen, & Robert Pergl. (2022). D2.8 FAIR Semantics Recommendations Third Iteration (V1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6675295>
The items below starting with P-Rec. are from this resource.
 - Daniel Garijo and Maria Poveda. Best Practices for Implementing FAIR Vocabularies and Ontologies on the Web. https://dgarijo.com/papers/best_practices2020.pdf and <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2980/paper321.pdf>
- Stream B: Best practices for materials science practitioners to achieve FAIR data based on terminologies, schema, ontologies
- Planned:
 - Stream C: Elaborate harmonised terminologies and schema in materials sciences
 - Stream D: Adoption: Demonstrate FAIR terminologies, schema and ontologies